

Membrane potential based assay for SLC5A11 using HEK-293 SLC5A11 OE cells

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Assay description

FLIPR[®] membrane potential dye measures changes of charges across the cell membrane, upon activation of SLC5A11. The assay allows the detection of ion channel and transporter modulation by increasing or decreasing the fluorescent signal as cellular membrane potential changes. When cells are depolarized dye enters the cells, causing an increase in fluorescent signal, conversely, cells hyperpolarization results in dye exit and decreased fluorescence (Figure 1).

SLC5A11 has been identified as a Na⁺-coupled Myo-Inositol transporter that mediates an electrogenic transport (2 Na⁺, 1 Myo-inositol), eligible to be studied using the membrane potential dye.

Figure 1. Principal of a FLIPR[®] membrane potential dye assay. The assay measures changes of charges across the cell membrane, consequence of channels and transporters modulation. The fluorescent signal increases in intensity during membrane depolarization as dye follows the positively charged ions inside the cell. During membrane hyperpolarization, fluorescent signal decreases in intensity as dye follows the positively charged ions out of the cell.

Assay protocol

HEK-293 JumpIN-SLC5A11 cells were subjected to pharmacological characterization.

Cell preparation

Cells were detached from 80-90% confluent flasks and seeded at 10'000 cells/well in black-clear bottom poly-D-Lysine coated 384 well plate in medium without the selective antibiotics and incubated 24 hours at 37°C, 5% CO₂. At the same time of seeding cells were induced with 1 µg/mL Doxycycline (not induced and mock control in parallel).

Membrane Potential assay

Medium was removed and cells were incubated 30 minutes at RT in 20 µL/well of FMP-Blue-Dye (0.5X dye dissolved in Standard Tyrode's Buffer as indicated in the manufacturer manual) and plates analysed at FLIPR^{TETRA} reader using a λexc 510 - 545nm / λem 565 - 625 nm filter.

Phlorizin inhibitor was tested at a concentration of 500 µM directly dissolved in the FMP-Blue-Dye solution and incubated therefore for 30 min at RT.

To test pharmacology 20 µL/well of Myo-Inositol DR (2X in Standard Tyrode's Buffer), starting from 5 mM, 1:5 dilution steps (8 concentrations, only buffer included) was online injected at the plate reader and fluorescence recorded.

Data analysis

FLIPR^{TETRA} measurements obtained from different well replicates were analysed by using the Screenworks software (Molecular Devices, Version 3.0.1.4). Absolute Response (RFU) is obtained applying "Subtract Bias on Sample: n" (where n = Timepoint of compound injection) whereas Assay Window Response (ΔF/F0) is obtained applying "Response over Baseline" correction (where Baseline = Timepoint -1 and -2 before activator injection) and "Background Subtraction". Data were then exported as Area Under the Curve (AUC). Mean and standard deviation of each replicate were calculated on the exported data with Excel software, then values were used to create sigmoidal dose-response curves (variable slope) and to calculate EC50/IC50 values with GraphPad PRISM software (Version 6).

Additional information

Target data

SLC	SLC5A11
Synonyms	Sodium/Myo-Inositol Cotransporter 2, SMIT2
SLC sub-family	Solute Carrier Family 5 (Sodium/Inositol Cotransporter)
UniProt ID	Q8WWX8
RESOLUTE Cell ID	CE02HH-S (HEK-SLC5A11-WTOE-p1)

Assay data

	Compound name (1)	Myo-Inositol
	PubChem CID	892
	Vendor (catalogue #)	Sigma Aldrich, # I7508
	Mode of action	Substrate
	Standard value type (i.e EC50, PoC, etc)	EC ₅₀ = 104 μM

Discussion

The Membrane Potential Assay for SLC5A11 showed a specific and dose-dependent fluorescent signal upon injection of increasing doses of Myo-Inositol. The increase in the fluorescence intensity is a result of cell depolarization that reflects the co-transport of Na⁺ through the transporter together with the substrate. Phorizin did not affect this specific fluorescence signal.

Cross references

- RESOLUTE report at [Zenodo](#).